

OpenRiskNet

RISK ASSESSMENT E-INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable Report D2.2

Initial API version provided to providers of services

This project is funded by
the European Union

OpenRiskNet: Open e-Infrastructure to Support Data Sharing, Knowledge
Integration and in silico Analysis and Modelling in Risk Assessment

Project Number 731075

www.openrisknet.org

Project identification

Grant Agreement	731075
Project Name	OpenRiskNet: Open e-Infrastructure to Support Data Sharing, Knowledge Integration and in silico Analysis and Modelling in Risk Assessment
Project Acronym	OpenRiskNet
Project Coordinator	Douglas Connect GmbH
Star date	1 December 2016
End date	30 November 2019
Duration	36 Months
Project Partners	P1 Douglas Connect GmbH Switzerland (DC) P2 Johannes Gutenberg-Universitat Mainz, Germany (JGU) P3 Fundacio Centre De Regulacio Genomica, Spain (CRG) P4 Universiteit Maastricht, Netherlands (UM) P5 The University Of Birmingham, United Kingdom (UoB) P6 National Technical University Of Athens, Greece (NTUA) P7 Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Foerderung Der Angewandten Forschung E.V., Germany (Fraunhofer) P8 Uppsala Universitet, Sweden (UU) P9 Medizinische Universitat Innsbruck, Austria (MUI) P10 Informatics Matters Limited, United Kingdom (IM) P11 Institut National de l'environnement et des Risques, France (INERIS)

Deliverable Report identification

Document ID and title	Deliverable 2.2 Initial API version provided to providers of services
Deliverable Type	Demonstrator
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Work Package	WP2
Task(s)	Task 2.2 API specification and semantic interoperability
Deliverable lead partner	JGU
Author(s)	Micha Rautenberg (JGU) Andreas Karwath (JGU) Stefan Kramer (JGU) Tim Dudgeon (IM) Ola Spjuth (UU) Daniel Bachler (DC) Thomas Exner (DC) Joh Dokler (DC) Haralambos Sarimveis (NTUA) Angelos Valsamis (NTUA) Philip Doganis (NTUA) Egon Willighagen (UM) Frederic Bois (INERIS)
Status	Final
Version	V1.0
Document history	2017-05-12 Draft ready for review 2017-05-31 Final version

Table of Contents

SUMMARY	5
INTRODUCTION	6
REQUIREMENTS	7
REVIEW OF EXISTING STANDARDS	8
Background APIs	8
OpenTox	8
ToxBank	9
eNanoMapper	9
Open PHACTS	10
Background Ontologies	11
Domain Ontologies	11
Phenotype and Trait Ontology	11
BioAssay Ontology	11
CHEMINF Ontology	11
Environment Ontology	12
EDAM Ontology	12
Application Ontologies	12
eNanoMapper Ontology	12
Experimental Factor Ontology	12
DESIGN CONCEPT AND INTEROPERABILITY LAYER	13
STEPWISE API DESIGN	15
Step 1: identify and collect the available data and tools	16
Step 2: provide description of data and services	16
Step 3: analyze the available descriptions and look for patterns	16
Step 4: annotate the existing definitions and make the transition to linked data	17
Step 5: decide on (or develop) the underlying discoverability protocol	17
Open Api	17
Hydra	18
SERVICE DISCOVERY	19
Goals	19
Outline of the interaction of a service with the service registry	19
USE CASES	21
PUBLISHING OF THE INITIAL API FOR SERVICE PROVIDERS	26
OUTLOOK ON UPCOMING OPENRISKNET API DEVELOPMENT	26
API Time Plan	26
CONCLUSIONS	27

ABBREVIATIONS	28
REFERENCES	29
ANNEXES	31
Use Cases Description	31
Use Case Template	31
Use Case 1: Merge existing data by a common structure identifier	32
Use Case 2: Building a (predictive) model	34
Use Case 3: Search and Retrieve Assay Data based on Ontological Terms	36

SUMMARY

This document reports the work towards the first version of the OpenRiskNet application programming interfaces (APIs) to be released to all partners of the consortium and associated partners for feedback and usage. Based on the diversity of the requirement foreseeable when developing the case studies to validate the infrastructure with real-world applications across all areas of predictive toxicology and risk assessment, a bottom-up approach to start with existing APIs and then harmonize them and bring them collectively to higher levels by integrating richer scientific annotation (semantic interoperability layer) was adopted in contrast to a top-down approach, where the API specification is defined by the consortium first and then all services have to be changed to comply to this specification. The ongoing efforts to collect and describe the available services in a standardized way will be continued by specifying guidelines for the semantic annotation of the services taking new and emerging semantic web standards like Open API 3.0 and Hydra into account. In parallel, the manually curated inventory of available services and their API descriptions will be transformed into an automated service discovery by querying the information about their capabilities through the added semantic interoperability layer. Already defined or new use cases, which are meant to test specific areas of the infrastructure and which will become part of the case studies later, are used to continuously validate the concepts and their implementation and have already proven sensible for the decision to move from a top-down to a bottom-up approach for the API development.

INTRODUCTION

The OpenRiskNet Consortium develops the OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure for the harmonisation and improved interoperability of data and software tools in the area of predictive toxicology and risk assessment. It will combine interoperable web services providing data or analysis, processing and modelling tools communicating over well-defined and harmonized application programming interfaces (APIs) supplemented by a semantic interoperability layer added to every service to describe the functionality whilst guaranteeing the technical and semantic interoperability. In computer programming, an API is a set of clearly defined methods of communication between various software components. More precisely, it is a set of subroutine definitions, protocols, and tools for building application software. A good API makes it easier to develop computer programs by providing specifications for all the software building blocks. An API specification can take many forms, depending whether it applies to a web-based tool, operating system, database, computer hardware or software library. For examples of APIs, see the C++ Standard Template Library, POSIX, or Microsoft Windows API. Previous projects like OpenTox, Open PHACTS and eNanoMapper created a set of APIs, which were designed for the specific problems at hand like creating, validating and applying a QSAR model or bringing together pharmacological data resources and which build the starting point for the OpenRiskNet developments. However, the additional requirements of OpenRiskNet as already envisioned and seen in the use cases developed and described below or under development for testing parts of the infrastructure as well as the larger case studies for validating the complete infrastructure, especially the much broader scope covering all areas of predictive toxicology and risk assessment as well as the semantic annotation of the APIs needed for the interoperability layer, render extensions and improvements of the existing API concepts absolutely inevitable, which will be described in this document.

REQUIREMENTS

In the OpenRiskNet description of action, the main goals of the project were summarized as

- identify and integrate relevant data and knowledge sources;
- identify and integrate both algorithms and tools covering all important areas for risk assessment including toxicity predictions, toxicogenomics, biokinetics modelling, in vitro - in vivo extrapolation;
- support the end user with tools for data input into OpenRiskNet-compliant databases, as well as with tools for data visualization and reporting.
- consolidate existing application programming interfaces from OpenTox, eNanoMapper, ToxBank and other relevant resources (e.g. Open PHACTS, PubChem) and create APIs to support the OpenRiskNet interoperability layer
- develop an interoperability layer, which can be accessed directly by users so as to understand the capabilities and input requirements of a specific service as well as retrieve additional information for example the scientific and technological background;
- enable the connection to services running on external infrastructures (like HPC environments);

The approach taken in the OpenRiskNet infrastructure to fulfill these requirements is based on interoperable web services, which communicate over well-defined, harmonized APIs supplemented by semantic annotations. Due to their pivotal role in the formation of the complete infrastructure, the API concepts need to be specified early in the project and then be tested and evaluated in real-world applications specified in the OpenRiskNet case studies. To agree to a common understanding as well as starting point for the API development, a meeting was organized in Mainz (16-17 January 2017), in which three initial API use case examples were outlined (see section Use Cases) for testing specific aspects of the API concept and the following guiding principles for the development were defined specifically considering the requirements added by the semantic interoperability layer:

- Data sets and other information (services) will be broadcasted on multiple levels (locally or globally).
- Semi-automatic matching, e.g. semi-automatic comparison of compound information, will be performed based on meta-data (most likely based on annotations with ontologies).
- Simple integration into client applications has to be facilitated.
- Re-use of OpenTox (and associated) APIs is anticipated.
- Use of standard web-based technologies is anticipated.
- A versatile way of describing APIs is needed.
 - In a first instantiation Open API (*Swagger*) will be used.
 - Will be supplemented with something more powerful later.
- Prioritize resources based on provided API features and content.
- Processes have to be traceable and reproducible.
- Third party services can only be expected to provide partial descriptions (minimal set of required information needs to be defined).

REVIEW OF EXISTING STANDARDS

Background APIs

To demonstrate the need for further API development, we will review existing APIs from previous projects here shortly, which are used as starting point for the OpenRiskNet APIs, as well as ontologies anticipated for annotating in the semantic interoperability layer.

OpenTox

OpenTox APIs were designed to cover the field of QSAR-based predictive toxicology with dataset generation, model building, prediction and validation [1]. These APIs were developed, extended and refined during the EU funded FP7 projects OpenTox, ToxBank and eNanoMapper.

- OpenTox - An open source predictive toxicology framework 2008 - 2011
- ToxBank - Supporting integrated data analysis and servicing of alternative testing methods in toxicology 2011 - 2016
- eNanoMapper - A database and ontology framework for nanomaterials design and safety assessment 2014 - 2017

At the start of the 3 year FP7 OpenTox project a general agreement was that OpenTox will be a platform-independent collection of components that interact via well defined interfaces. The preferred form of communication between components had to be through web services. OpenTox components include services for data integration, model development, validation and reporting. A common API was defined for an interoperable infrastructure of compound, feature, dataset, algorithm, model, validation, report, ontology and task services. OpenTox selected Representational state transfer (REST) [2] as an architectural style for these distributed systems.

The RESTful OpenTox services are using HTTP methods to achieve uniform interfaces. The primary HTTP methods used are POST, GET, PUT and DELETE, corresponding to create, read, update and delete (CRUD) operations as known in any data processing. Response status of a HTTP request to a service is expressed by HTTP status codes [3].

To protect confidential data and resources in the framework, OpenTox defined also a pluggable Authorization and Authentication service with single-sign-on (SSO) mechanism that was included into the API.

OpenTox developed these specifications as an open standard to support the project internal, external and future development of web services in the field of toxicology.

All API definitions were collected on a webpage [4] and a manually generated OWL/RDF representation [5] was built in Protégé. RDF/XML was defined as a common data exchange format.

Two iterations with evaluations by developers from the community were made. That took the API to version 1.2.

Table 1. Example: RESTful OpenTox Feature service REST API

Description	Method	URI	Parameters	Result	Status codes
Get description of a specific feature definition	GET	/feature/{id}	[subjectid]	URI-list or RDF representation of a feature	200,404,503
Create a new feature	POST	/feature	[subjectid] Content-type ="any-of-RDF-types", content=RDF-representation	URI of the new feature definition	200,400,404,503
Update feature	PUT	/feature/{id}	[subjectid] Content-type ="any-of-RDF-types", content=RDF-representation	-	200,400,404,503
Delete feature	DELETE	/feature/{id}	[subjectid]	-	200,400,404,503
Get a list of available feature definitions	GET	/feature	[subjectid] ?query =URI-of-the-owl:sameAs-entry	URI list or RDF of features found by the query or all available, if query is empty Returns all features, for which owl:sameAs is given by the query	200,404,503

ToxBank

Based on OpenTox APIs the ToxBank Data Warehouse [6] has defined API extensions to handle diverse sets of biological experimental data (high throughput, omics, High Content Analysis) and bioinformatics analysis. The ToxBank API [7] definition was documented in semantic mediawiki with semantic forms for its additional web services Protocol, Investigation, Search, User, Alert, Organisation, Project, and Session services.

eNanoMapper

eNanoMapper [8] project used OpenTox APIs v 1.2 as an API standard [9]. Different components then extended the existing API specification to provide the necessary functionality. The extensions were mostly additional data querying endpoints that provided richer querying semantics.

Jagpot Quatro (JQ), the core modeling project of eNanoMapper, consists of a central API Gateway implemented in Java 8 and JEE7 that manages the flow of modelling, prediction and validation requests, wraps long running procedures to asynchronous tasks, provides authentication and authorisation mechanisms by communicating with OpenTox authorization and authentication services, and acts as a central RESTful Web endpoint for the whole system. Documentation for this public API is provided through *Swagger* [10] (now Open Api).

The API acts as a central endpoint for the whole JQ system, and orchestrates communication between the modeling microservices comprising the system and the outside world. Each JQ independent microservice, including the core API, is a purely stateless construct that allows

for individual replication and balancing, thus giving the ability to scale horizontally on any part of the system. By implementing functionality in such a microservice and polyglottal way, JQ is a cloud-ready application that uses the benefits of each platform for its own, having the ability to incorporate functionality by various established and open-source machine learning and data analysis toolkits. The orchestration and deployment of JQ services is handled by the containerization tool *Docker*, which provides a safe and isolated space for each microservice to run, while having its health monitored by the Docker daemon.

Finally, in the last stage of the project, JQ services introduced *JSON-LD* as a response serialization format, (formerly JSON, CSV and PDF were mainly used as response formats). This approach provided means for a semantic layer as well as the ease of use of JSON format.

Ambit, the core toxicological data management project used in eNanoMapper, REACH dossiers, and XMetDB [11], provides support for upload, search and retrieval of nanomaterials and experimental data through a REST web services API. It is implemented in Java and makes use of the Restlet library as well as the Jena RDF API . Ambit also uses *Swagger* [12] for demonstrating all RESTful resources contained, the HTTP Verbs that can be applied on each resource, as well as all supported representations. Ambit provides search functionalities for its data mainly through three types of search: toxicological endpoint search, chemical similarity search and semantic search via ontology free text search or via querying on a SPARQL endpoint.

During the eNanoMapper project the lazar framework for read across predictions was expanded for the prediction of nanoparticle toxicities, and a new methodology for calculating nanoparticle descriptors from core and coating structures was implemented. Nano-lazar [13] provides a flexible and reproducible framework for downloading data and ontologies from the open eNanoMapper infrastructure, developing and validating nanoparticle read across models, open-source code and a free graphical interface for nanoparticle read-across predictions. The nano-lazar webservice were adapted in order to provide REST interfaces that adhere to eNanoMapper standards and specifications and supplemented with interactive *Swagger* documentation and API definitions in *Swagger 2.0*.

Open PHACTS

Services provided by Open PHACTS are also made available with Open Api. These Open PHACTS web services are now provided by the Open PHACTS Foundation, but developed and previously hosted by an IMI-funded project [14]. The APIs expose a number of pre-competitive (and open) pharmacology datasets that support answering of twenty predefined research questions, selected based on expertise in the pharmaceutical industry [15]. To answer these questions, the API provides access to a number of integrated data sources, including ChEMBL [16][17], WikiPathways [18][19], UniProt [20] AERS, and others. The web service calls allow users to ask for all protein targets to which a drug or drug-like compound binds, all such compounds that bind to some target, or all biological pathways in which that target has a role.

Technically, the API is REST-based, but in the background these calls are translated to SPARQL queries using a variety of technologies associated with the Open PHACTS platform. For example, an identity resolution service (IRS) translates labels into identifiers, an identifier mapping service (IMS) overcomes the problem that different datasets use different identifiers, and the query expander takes a template SPARQL query and insert all alternatives identifiers before the query is executed on the SPARQL endpoint. A configuration file specifies various templates used, e.g. by the expander but also to provide the returned output to a format suitable for the Open Api endpoint. As the mention of the SPARQL endpoint already suggested, the pharmaceutical data sources are all integrated in the cache as semantic web (RDF) datasets. The API is a user-friendly wrapper around the private SPARQL endpoint.

Of particular interest to the use cases is one feature of the IMS in that it is aware of different levels of equivalence. For example, when discussing protein targets, the targets are commonly identified by protein identifiers. However, in biological pathways the corresponding gene identifier is more commonly used. Depending on the research question the protein can be seen as equivalent, but for other scientific questions you like to treat them as distinct. The same situation exists for drugs, where some databases contain the salt formation, while other databases contain the uncomplexed active ingredient. This concept has been formalized in the Open PHACTS projects as 'scientific lenses' [21]. The IMS comes with its own API, and can be used independently and is based on the BridgeDb framework [22].

Background Ontologies

Ontologies are approaches that structure the concepts and language used in a particular field. This section briefly discusses a number of ontologies and aspects related to selecting ontologies. Recent work in the life sciences field focused on overcoming a few essential open ends: first, much life sciences research, including in the areas of safety, have become very interdisciplinary and it is essential to reuse established ontologies [23]; second, many concepts are composites of simpler concepts, e.g. "concentration of compounds X" [24].

Ontology repositories (such as BioPortal [25] and the Ontology Lookup Service [26]) provide web services and interfaces to access ontologies and their content as well as more recently, following the Aber-OWL [27] paradigm, provide computational access to the semantic content of the ontologies and the inferences that can be drawn from them.

Domain Ontologies

Reuse of ontologies has the advantage that concepts have been established by a domain community, and frequently even a group of domain experts. Reproducing the effort they put in would be very costly and contradicting to the point of establishing a common community language. The next sections describe a few ontologies relevant to OpenRiskNet. This is not intended as means of providing a comprehensive list rather serving as an illustrative one.

Phenotype and Trait Ontology

The Phenotype and Trait Ontology (PATO, also called Phenotypic Quality Ontology) describes properties like phenotypes and traits [28]. It is frequently used in combination with other ontologies such as the Gene Ontology to refer to phenotypes. A recent paper shows how complex phenotypes can be modelled as combinations of simpler ontology terms [14] and provide formal class definitions. For example, 'abnormality of the face' can be composed of 'has part' some (quality and 'inheres in part of' some face). Toxicology has many such composed terms, and adoption of these axiomized terms should be encouraged.

BioAssay Ontology

While not the only ontology describing biological assays, the BioAssay Ontology (BAO) is certainly one of the larger projects [29]. The ontology has a detailed set of concepts by which assay experiments can be described. It has been used, for example, for assay data in PubChem [30].

CHEMINF Ontology

The Chemical Information ontology (CHEMINF) is an ontology describing the concepts of and

information about chemical entities [31]. The ontology is relevant for OpenRiskNet as it covers both experimental data and computational data and services. For example, it has a rich section of chemical identifiers and molecular descriptors.

Environment Ontology

The Environment Ontology (ENVO) is an ontology that can be used to describe environment aspects of research [32]. As such, it can be used to annotate ecotoxicology data, as is done in the eNanoMapper project.

EDAM Ontology

The EDAM ontology is one aimed at annotating operations, topics, and data formats with common concepts, creating a hierarchy aimed at convenience, allowing organisation and finding services and tools for a specific term [33]. One of the uses of EDAM is in bio.tools, where it is used to give detailed information about inputs and outputs of bioinformatics web services [34].

Application Ontologies

In contrast to the general ontologies listed above, an application ontology is engineered for a specific use or application focus and we will concentrate here on the two most relevant for OpenRiskNet.

eNanoMapper Ontology

The eNanoMapper ontology is a typical application ontology [9]. While it is based on the Basic Formal Ontology [35], it has a pragmatic approach with a focus on the existing data and the dissemination of that knowledge to support the design of safe nanomaterials. Due to the broadness of the research field that eNanoMapper is meant to be applied to, the ontology is comprised of parts derived from multiple other ontologies. But rather than combining those upstream ontologies, it selects only those parts of the ontology that are needed by the nanosafety research community, and then these are projected to a BFO-based hierarchy, i.e. categorized under ontological terms like continuant, occurrent, etc. [36]. This ensures the terms from upstream ontologies are part of the eNanoMapper ontology, in a harmonized hierarchy. Second, the eNanoMapper ontology will only include one upstream ontology term and disregard similar terms from other upstream ontologies. This integration process was automated using the Slimmer tool and updated whenever changes are made, using the Jenkins building and testing environment (*see also D2.1*).

Experimental Factor Ontology

The Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) is another application ontology primarily developed to annotate the experimental variables used in EMBL-EBI databases [37]. That includes factors in the areas of disease, anatomy, cell type, chemical compounds, and assay information. For this it reuses frequently other ontologies, such as Uberon [38] and ChEBI [39].

DESIGN CONCEPT AND INTEROPERABILITY LAYER

Two main reasons prohibit the direct, unmodified use of the API concepts described above: 1) the much broader scope of data and tool services, which will be integrated and harmonized in OpenRiskNet compared to OpenTox, Open PHACTS and eNanoMapper and 2) the additional demands imposed by the semantic interoperability layer.

OpenTox has developed a framework for creating, validating and using QSAR models in predictive toxicology and eNanoMapper extended this to nanomaterial safety. The Open PHACTS APIs were designed to bring together pharmacological data resources. Therefore, all have a well defined and focused scope, which could be modelled directly into the API design concept. Building on and combining these previous efforts but at the same time largely extending the area of application and the targeted stakeholders, OpenRiskNet is trying to bring together all aspects of chemical and nanomaterial risk assessment including access to data sources and processing, analysis and modelling tools from areas such as hazard prediction using read across or QSAR, toxicogenomics and biokinetics modelling and as a European infrastructure it needs to be sustainable and prepared for future extensions regarding the integrated data types and modelling approaches. This is only possible with a more flexible approach, which on one hand allows for extensions but on the other hand avoids too much variety jeopardizing the interoperability of the services. One example of a limitation introduced in e.g. the OpenTox APIs is that all services need to follow the pass-by-reference semantic. For instance, when running a prediction using a QSAR model the client software does a HTTP POST/GET command passing in the URIs of the dataset to be predicted, the algorithm to run and the model to use. Whilst this is beneficial for very large datasets, a simpler task like translating one chemical identifier into another could transmit the data immediately using pass-by-value semantics. Being more flexible by allowing both options would facilitate the integration of more external services especially as long as they are not completely OpenRiskNet compatible.

Additionally, OpenRiskNet will work on making the interfaces smarter by adding a semantic interoperability layer. By querying this layer, a service should provide the following information to be compliant to the OpenRiskNet infrastructure:

- Scientific background of the service, this can just be a link to the relevant publication but also to manuals, tutorials and other training material;
- Technical background like links to source code, installation instructions, license information and deployment options;
- Capabilities of the service, for databases this will include, amongst others, the used data schemata, i.e. the description of the stored data and the associated metadata, as well as search options and, for software tools, the type and amount of generated output including the options and parameters which can be chosen by the user to optimize the results and
- Requirement on input data types and formats and options on the output format.

The standards used in the previous projects provide only limited functionality to document the APIs in the form of *Swagger* definitions and are not able to attach such information-rich annotations queryable with the API endpoints. Whilst the Jaqpot Quattro service already uses JSON-LD for semantic annotation, the recent release of Open API specification 3.0 opens up possibilities to annotate data and computational tools in a standardized way. However, since this specification is new and still evolving, more experience has to be gained on the best design options and to see if it is even applicable to the challenges to be tackled by the OpenRiskNet project.

For such a testing and validation of the new approaches adopted in the infrastructure, the

concept of case studies was introduced in the project. As described in more detail below, they will apply the OpenRiskNet services and workflows to real-world examples from risk assessment. However, subparts of the infrastructure and especially the functionality and usability of the APIs should be tested as soon as possible in parallel to their development. Use cases will be used for this and three have already been defined based on applications from previous projects. While many of the simpler aspects of the use cases could be addressed with the existing API concepts, the more complex scenarios will require the fuller semantic interoperability aspects of OpenRiskNet. When looking at the diverse set of requirements in these use cases as well as the ones under earlier stages of development and not listed here (reverse dosimetry, toxicogenomics workflow, comprehensive view on compound), it became clear that a top-down approach, where the OpenRiskNet consortium publishes the specifications for OpenRiskNet compliant APIs and then asks associated partners to adapt their software to these, will result in many iteration cycles until the requirements of all the different areas of risk assessment will be satisfied. Additionally, if the first iterations of the APIs are based on only a subset of the types of services, which need to be supported, design decisions made in these can only be undone with large effort if they prove to be unfit for types of services added later. OpenTox can be used as an example here. Due to its goal to generate a framework for QSAR modelling, the API endpoints like compound, feature, dataset and algorithm were specifically chosen. The concept of a molecular “feature” is very specific to QSAR and is not needed for other areas like toxicogenomics. In contrast, new concepts have to be added to integrate e.g different types of databases, physicochemical characterisation services especially for nanomaterials and biokinetic modelling tools. Therefore, it was decided to change the design concept to a bottom-up approach, described in more detail in the next section, in which the existing concepts and APIs of partners and associated partners are collected and consolidated first. These will then be harmonized and made interoperable by moving them all more or less at the same time to state-of-the-art API specifications like Open API 3.0 and integrating detailed descriptions and semantic annotations in a stepwise manner.

STEPWISE API DESIGN

With the growing amount of biological / toxicological data available, two problems arise: first, the problem of *findability* (i.e. how to find the available data) and second, the problem of *interoperability* (i.e. how to use, combine and harmonize this data and make use of it as one unit). There are a number of domain specific efforts across different projects that aim to solve both mentioned problems.

In the space of data findability there are e.g.

- Biosharing [<https://biosharing.org/>]
- Bio.tools [<https://bio.tools/>]

In the space of data interoperability e.g.

- Open PHACTS [<https://www.openphacts.org/>]
- BioSchemas [<http://bioschemas.org/>]

Most of the listed approaches base the work on linked data [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Linked_data] and associated technologies. Bizer et al. [40] define linked data as “a method of publishing structured data so that it can be interlinked and become more useful through semantic queries. It builds upon standard Web technologies such as HTTP, RDF and URIs, but rather than using them to serve web pages for human readers, it extends them to share information in a way that can be read automatically by computers. This enables data from different sources to be connected and queried.” The data parts (or associated problems) of OpenRiskNet are closely aligned with the wider domain outlined above. Therefore it makes sense to adopt the solutions to these approaches.

However, the aim of OpenRiskNet is not only data but also operations over data and exposure of these operations via APIs. This is a space that is much less explored. There are existing general approaches, technologies and standards available (e.g. Open Api [<https://www.openapis.org/>], JSON API [<http://jsonapi.org/>]) but there are no existing standards to handle operations (and APIs) in the domain of Linked data.

It is important to observe that when it comes to operations over data, both problems of findability and interoperability apply as well. It would therefore be desirable to treat them in a similar way to data or at least with the same toolset. If we take for granted that the solutions will be sought in the space of Linked Data, it is worthwhile considering how to approach this. Given the OpenRiskNet setup where partners will contribute data services and tools services (operations) that will then be made discoverable and interoperable, two approaches present themselves.

First, the top-down approach where the consortium would define the complete semantic layer and then the partners would implement against that.

Second, the bottom-up approach where the partners first specify what their datasets and tools are and then the semantic layer is developed around this information.

We believe that the bottom-up approach is more appropriate for OpenRiskNet for the following reasons:

- When it comes to implementation of linked data solutions it is important to strike the right balance between generality and specificity. If a solution is too general, then everything is possible but the level of interoperability might be reduced or consuming such services might become prohibitively complicated. If a solution is too specific, then a higher level of interoperability is possible but the scope can be too limiting. Understanding the domain (list of operations and data shapes) first is therefore of great benefit.
- While people are understanding the concept of linked data more and more, some of

the underlying technologies are still relatively new, evolving and not everyone has experience in using them. To ease the entry into this space it is therefore beneficial to take a gradual approach from the non-linked data solutions to the linked data solutions and break the process into manageable chunks of work.

The more detailed proposal of this process is as follows:

Step 1: identify and collect the available data and tools

In this step, the OpenRiskNet partners have identified the data and tools they want to include in the core part of the infrastructure provided by the OpenRiskNet consortium and will continue to do so throughout the project to enrich the infrastructure with services from associated partners.. The information collected at this step is:

- Title or name of a dataset or tool
- Short description
- Possible URL(s) where the data or tools are currently available
- Partner name (organisation)
- Contact person (name, email)

This information is now used to establish a registry of all the components involved in the OpenRiskNet and track their status (see <https://openrisknet.org>).

Step 2: provide description of data and services

In this ongoing step, the OpenRiskNet partners will provide a more detailed description of the datasets and tools to be included in the OpenRiskNet. At this stage they are free to describe the existing or planned objects without any constraints related to the API endpoints or data shapes. However, the partners will provide the descriptions in a unified way. To facilitate this, we propose to use the Open Api specification 3.0 [41] (currently rc2) which should cover both data and operations definitions. When it comes to operations it is especially important for partners to describe both inputs and outputs.

Step 3: analyze the available descriptions and look for patterns

In this step WP2 and WP4 will look at the provided definitions and look for the following patterns:

- Common data types (e.g. compound)
- Common operation types (e.g. molecular identifier conversion)

WP2 and WP4 will use the identified patterns and harmonize the underlying types (use existing definitions where available and formally define new ones). WP2 and WP4 will at this step also propose a set of preferred vocabularies and ontologies that partners could use to annotate their definitions (in the next step).

A couple of points regarding the types are in order here. When it comes to operations it is very important to define operation inputs (types) and outputs (types). This provides means to match and combine the different operations and therefore provide higher level of interoperability. To use an analogy from the functional programming languages, if function f takes type a and returns type b ($f : a \rightarrow b$) and function g takes type b and returns type c ($g : b \rightarrow c$) one can chain them in the following way: $g.f : a \rightarrow c$. This in turn opens the possibility to develop workflow systems that have well defined underlying semantics.

Furthermore, operations themselves can be annotated which provides a means for

discoverability. For example, if all operations dealing with the chemical ID conversion are annotated as such (provided that such a concept is defined), it is possible to build user interfaces where users can browse through different operations and in combination with type information decide which are the most appropriate for them, regardless of the actual chemical ID used by a particular service.

Step 4: annotate the existing definitions and make the transition to linked data

In this step, partners will annotate existing definitions with vocabulary and ontology terms and by doing so, build the linked data semantic layer. Here the actual implementation details will become of great importance. There are a couple of reasons for this.

First, it is reasonable to expect that sections of definitions will be hard to annotate since there simply may not be appropriate definitions available.

Second, the choice of tools will have an impact on the actual implementations and the ease-of-use for the developers.

Having these two constraints in mind we propose JSON-LD [<http://json-ld.org/>] as a serialization format. There are three important reasons for this:

- Most developers are already familiar with JSON and enjoy the ease of use JSON provides. Therefore the use of JSON-LD lowers the barrier of adoption and makes the transition from non-linked data to linked data almost seamless.
- Since JSON-LD allows for blank nodes [<https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld/#dfn-blank-node>] to be used for predicates, it makes cases where users may not find appropriate terms less severe (and still technically correct). More on this subject can be found here: <http://manu.sporny.org/2013/rdf-identifiers/>
- JSON-LD provides means to split the annotations and the data by providing the option to pass the JSON-LD context in the HTTP response link header [<https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld/#interpreting-json-as-json-ld>]. This is an important implementation detail that allows developers to migrate their existing APIs without modifying the underlying response building code.

Step 5: decide on (or develop) the underlying discoverability protocol

The findability requirement of the OpenRiskNet demands that all the APIs expose the information about their capabilities in a unified manner and make it available for consumption to the discovery service(s).

Currently we identified two possible solutions but given that both are under active development we need to postpone the decision on which one to use. Also, findings from steps 1-4 may provide further means for a more educated choice. Below is the outline of the two possible approaches along with the identified benefits and downsides.

Open Api

Open Api v3 [42] (*Swagger v2*) is an API documentation specification. It provides means for API developers to define API endpoints (operations) including their inputs and outputs. A tools ecosystem is available around this specification that allows, for example, generation of interactive documentation from the API specification.

The benefits of choosing Open Api lie in the fact that many developers are already familiar with it and the fact that it is becoming prominent in the API design community. Also, we are

proposing to use Open Api v3 in step 2.

The downside of Open Api is that it is currently not targeting linked data but rather traditional REST APIs that use JSON as a serialisation mechanism. This means we would have to extend Open Api to provide for the desired semantic layer. Open Api does provide means for introducing extensions using the x- attributes and these could be used to achieve our goal but of course these extensions would be non-standard ones. Combining this with the JSON-LD properties such as allowing blank nodes for properties and the possible separation between response bodies and context, this may be a feasible solution.

Finally, Open Api does not uniquely prescribe the API envelope (paging, query parameter formation) which is usually needed and is important when it comes to API integration. We could use ideas from the JSON API [<http://jsonapi.org/>] specification to define those.

Hydra

Hydra [43] is a vocabulary for hypermedia driven APIs. Its aim is to solve the same problem as Open Api is solving for the traditional REST APIs but for linked data. It uses JSON-LD as a serialisation mechanism and also provides ready-to use means for API navigation including paging.

The benefits of using Hydra are that it targets linked data and therefore seamlessly combines the linked data and API definitions using the same (linked data) tools.

Hydra is not yet a W3C specification and is in a draft state (January 16 2017). As a consequence it might still change. Another consideration is available tooling around the Hydra specification. While the general linked data tools could be used to work with Hydra API specifications it is often helpful in API design to have more specific tooling available. So to provide a better assessment of this point we will collect more hands-on experience using Hydra.

SERVICE DISCOVERY

Besides the interoperability tasks, OpenRiskNet will provide a set of technological solutions for virtual research environments (VRE) that make it possible to deploy OpenRiskNet services and reproduce any computational analysis in a reproducible and scalable way on most hardware like local workstations, computing centres and cloud services or can be run as a service (more information is available from deliverable report D2.1). Inside an OpenRiskNet VRE, several services will be running alongside each other (e.g. modelling services, data services) and they will communicate with each other via a shared network. The Service Discovery problem is then the question of how these various services find each other so that they can work together (e.g. a risk assessment application might want to know what data sources and modeling services are available inside the VRE).

The easiest solution would be to hard-code and permanently interlink the services (using DNS service names), but this would defeat the flexibility and extensibility goals of OpenRiskNet. Instead, we see the need for a central service registry that is a prerequisite for a functional VRE. This service registry can then be queried to find out about the services running in the VRE at any given time.

Goals

The primary goals of the service registry are:

- Allow services to find the DNS name, port and service descriptions of other active services in the VRE
- Allow services to be registered when they are started (this could be done utilizing the docker/kubernetes runtime environment events)
- Allow queries based on the service description metadata (Open Api descriptions) of the services that are registered.
- It is desirable to be able to declare external services that are not hosted within the VRE and add them to the registry (e.g. to declare a subset of the ChEMBL REST API so that it can automatically be found as a resource).

The following is a list of concerns that are explicitly not within the scope of a service registry solution for OpenRiskNet (at least for the first iteration):

- Authentication against the service registry itself – at least for the first iteration of the registry we assume that if a service is running within a VRE and has network access to the service registry it is allowed to add new entries and query for existing services.
- Load balancing - service registries often serve a double purpose of load balancing among a pool of actual instances that serve any particular service. When building on top of kubernetes, such a load balancing is already performed by the kubernetes service primitive and thus does not need to be handled by the service registry.

Outline of the interaction of a service with the service registry

To illustrate in more detail how the service registry should work, first imagine a simple case of an empty VRE. Three services are deployed into that VRE and should work together: a data service, a modelling service and a risk assessment web application.

1. The VRE is provisioned and the service registry starts
2. The data service is added to the VRE. It is started as a docker container and is automatically discovered by the service registry based on e.g. kubernetes events and labels that describe where this service can be queried for its service description.

3. The modelling service is started in a similar way to the data service and is registered.
4. The risk assessment web application is started. It registers itself as above, then queries the service registry for available data and modelling services based on a number of constraints (e.g. accepting certain chemical identifiers, ...). These constraints could be ontology terms that are used to annotate the service descriptions of all OpenRiskNet services.
5. A user interacts with the web application that in turn queries both the data service and the modelling service to fulfill the user's commands.
6. When any of these services is shut down the service registry should learn about this (either by listening to lifetime events or by health checks).

The service registry/discovery will be a crucial piece of the ORN infrastructure that is intimately tied to the semantic interoperability layer as it will need to parse this information of all available services and provide rich query functionality so that the services will be found by users and other services. The implementation of such a service is thus dependent on a decision of the encoding of the semantic interoperability layer described above. However, several key technologies have already been identified for the implementation (e.g. use of Kubernetes service lifetime events via the Kubernetes API [<https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/kubernetes-api/>], a JSON based serializations format, HTTP as a transport protocol). Furthermore, we plan to maintain an API compatible, manually curated list of services while the service registry is in development to facilitate the development of tools depending on the service registry. The development of the service registry is scheduled to be finished in time for the M18 milestone and will be available to OpenRiskNet partners for beta-testing ahead of time.

USE CASES

As described in the introduction, the main objectives of the OpenRiskNet project are to provide to the predictive toxicology and risk assessment community solutions regarding availability, quality, harmonization, interoperability, standardization and sustainability of data and software tools and to overcome related issues like fragmentation of data and tools and poor explanation and insufficient details on experimental and computational study design and protocols applied. Case studies will be used to test and evaluate the solutions especially including the developed APIs and the interoperability layer regarding their capabilities to satisfy the requirements of the different stakeholder groups including researchers, risk assessors and regulators. These present real-world applications like systems biology approaches for grouping compounds, read-across applications using chemical and biological similarity, and identifying areas of concern based on in vitro and in silico approaches for compounds lacking any previous knowledge from animal experiments (ab initio case). WP1 is actively developing detailed case study definitions and will make them available to WP2 and WP4 as soon as possible at least in parts even before the deadline of Deliverable 1.3 “Final definition of case studies” at M12. Even if the full set of requirements will only be available and the applicability of the infrastructure in real-world setting can only be fully tested when the case study definitions are finalized, testing and validation of basic concepts considered, even if only in part, has to be done in parallel to the development to identify issues as soon as possible. To be able to do so, fully elaborated subparts of the case studies have been translated into three use cases (more will follow in the area of reverse dosimetry, toxicogenomics workflow, comprehensive view on compound) to evaluate important key components of the infrastructure. This approach has already proven sensible. Requirements seen when specifying the more complex scenarios of these cases requiring the fuller semantic interoperability aspects of OpenRiskNet brought us to the conclusion that a top-down approach for specifying the APIs could result in suboptimal, too narrow definitions of endpoints and the collection of existing APIs and bringing them to higher level in a bottom-up way is more appropriate. Exemplary pseudocode was created (<https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/home/wiki/Use-Cases> also accessible through the project website), which will now guide the prioritization of data sources and tools to be integrated and used as first examples to improve the level of the corresponding APIs regarding the harmonization of the API endpoints, service description and semantic annotation. A short introduction to the scientific (sub)goals pursued and the technical subareas of the infrastructure probed by the use cases is given below and a more detailed description can be found in the Annex.

UC1: Merge existing data by a common structure identifier

This use case describes the need to generate a consistent set of data by merging multiple individual datasets. An example would be generating activities for a set of structures against a particular enzyme target. The dataset generated could be the input for building a predictive model (see UC2). The assumption is that data for individual assays are accessible as datasets through an API (e.g. ChEMBL or PubChem web services) and that there is some mechanism for the user to select particular datasets from those that are available. Multiple datasets are merged into a single dataset based on identification of structures that are common between the datasets.

This use case is intended to indicate the capabilities of the infrastructure regarding data APIs. In the first step, the existing APIs will be evaluated regarding the search and download possibilities and how the data can then be transformed to get a harmonized view across the

different data sources. The equality of the assays and the comparability of the data in the different databases has to be evaluated manually by the user but this will be more and more automated based on the semantic interoperability layer during later development steps of this use case.

Figure 1. UC1: Extract of UC1. For the complete technical description see Annex

UC2: Building and using a prediction model

Use case 2 describes the process of building predictive models from OpenRiskNet compliant datasets and applying the generated models on prediction datasets. Datasets used for training and prediction, can be the result of use case 1.

This use case can evaluate the progress of modeling APIs' integration into the OpenRiskNet ecosystem. It can test the maturity of the semantic interoperability layer to efficiently distinguish if a training dataset is compatible with an algorithm and if a prediction dataset is

compatible with a prediction model. Moreover, the modeling APIs are required to publish the generated models and datasets accompanied with semantic metadata on their life cycle, whenever requested. Thus, this use case will also be able to evaluate the process of semantically enriching the dynamically created entities.

Use Case 2: Building a (predictive) model

Diagram:

Name:

Building and using a prediction model

Brief Description:

A user applies an algorithm to a dataset and uses the resulting model on a different dataset. The results are stored as novel dataset within the system.

Actors:

A researcher with background in model building.

Basic Flow:

The user selects an algorithm and a dataset within the system to induce a model. The selection of the algorithm is based on the intended uses, i.e. within a supervised setting using a classification or regression algorithm. The algorithm possesses a number of default parameters, which can be adjusted to the users specifications. The user starts the induction process. Upon termination of the algorithm the user receives the result in form of a model. The user can supply an already existing second dataset and apply the model to it. The results are returned as novel dataset URI.

Figure 2. UC2: Extract of UC2. For the complete technical description see Annex

UC3: Searching nanomaterial repositories for experimental data linked to known key events

For Key Events (KEs) in Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) to be useful in decision making, the event needs to be observable. That is, an experimental measurement needs to indicate that the key event happens and will trigger downstream events. Various other European projects are working on linking KEs to bioassays (EU-ToxRisk, etc.), but to explore this potential link, we need an infrastructure to allow researchers to find experimental data for some type of assay for some type of (nano)material. One aspect of that is to find omics data for a particular material.

Use Case 3 describes the basic process of finding and retrieving omics data related to a nanomaterial and a specific KE. The KE is related to some bioassay, and using an ontology approach, e.g. with BioAssay ontology terms can be used to query databases with experimental omics data.

This use case can evaluate the progress of the ontology services as well as the coupling of ontological terms with regards to data and assays. Using additional resources that link AOP KEs to genes, proteins, or assays, such as those being set up on the WikiPathways AOP Portal (<http://aop.wikipathways.org>), it generated a needed level of interoperability to support and possibly validate the European research for replacing animal testing with AOP-guided *in vitro* omics approaches.

Use Case 3: Search and Retrieve Assay Data based on Ontological Terms

Diagram:

Name:

Search and Retrieve Molecular Data linked to Key Events in AOPs using assay ontology terms

Brief Description:

A user wants to look up omics data for a particular bioassay. The user supplies a particular assay type, fetches related ontological terms from an ontology service, and retrieves all available assay data associated with assay types and terms. The use case is aimed at nanomaterials, but can be extended to other chemical substances, including compounds.

Actors:

A researcher with background in toxicology and assay technologies.

Basic Flow:

The user starts with a type of assay, like a genotoxicity assay. This term is looked up in an ontology service (i.e. containing the eNanoMapper ontology or the BioAssay Ontology) and the results are used to retrieve matching assays using the assay service (i.e. containing the nanosafety data repository). Using these results, the assay service is employed to retrieve data annotated with the specific ontology terms. Furthermore, the call to the ontology service may return multiple term IRIs if a full ontological hierarchy is requested. This simplifies asking all genotoxicity assay data, even if data is annotated with more specific genotoxicity assay terms.

Figure 3. UC3: Extract of UC3. For the complete technical description see Annex

PUBLISHING OF THE INITIAL API FOR SERVICE PROVIDERS

The concept described in this document are also available from the project's webpage <https://openrisknet.org>. The data and software services including specifications on their APIs as well as the categorization regarding their API development levels (according to step 1-5 described above) can be reached from there as well or directly at <https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/openapi-examples>. Updates to the API specifications will be continuously published as a reference for all project developers on the OpenRiskNet wiki at <https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/home/wiki> according to the time plan below.

OUTLOOK ON UPCOMING OPENRISKNET API DEVELOPMENT

The concept of the initial API with its stepwise design approach will be reviewed, revised and extended in order to meet the requirements of the ongoing development of the interoperability layer and case studies.

In month 24 the Deliverable 2.4: "Final API available for internal and external service providers" will be submitted. Specifications are reported on project website.

API Time Plan

Due Month	Task	Status
M1	Kick-off meeting initial discussions (API/Use Cases)	Completed
M2	API Meeting	Completed
M4	Initial Use case descriptions	Completed
M5	Discovery Service Discussion	Completed
M5	Interoperability & Semantic Layer Discussion	Completed
M6	Collect of existing APIs (step 1)	Completed
M7	Identification of service to be promoted to step 2 (Open API)	Scheduled
M9	Registry of available services online as starting point of service discovery	Scheduled
M10	Look for patterns in existing definitions and identification of services for transition to linked data (step 3 and 4)	Planned
M10	Development Hackathon (internal, Uppsala)	Scheduled
M12	API Hackathon (public, Basel)	Planned
M18	Development of the underlying discoverability protocol (step 5)	Scheduled
M18	MS5: Operational deployment of virtual infrastructures with service discovery and container orchestration	Scheduled
M24	MS8 Final API available for internal and external service providers	Scheduled

CONCLUSIONS

The OpenRiskNet project has adopted an approach for the development of harmonized and interoperable APIs, which has started by collecting available services and corresponding APIs as well as information on their capabilities and input/output options. Besides the list of services, which are provided by the OpenRiskNet consortium, we are in contact with a number of academic groups, institutes, agencies and SMEs, which are interested in becoming associated partners and will provide the information on their services to complement the tools available within the consortium and, in this way, to complete the picture on approaches used in the different areas of predictive toxicology and risk assessment.

Based on this collection, an overview on the requirements from all these areas can be obtained and integrated in the concepts for API harmonization and enriching the APIs with a semantic interoperability layer guaranteeing the right balance between genericity versus specificity of the API specification. The selected services will then be upgraded in a stepwise manner to provide the semantic description first in a human- and then in a computer-readable form based on ontology annotations. This work as well as the resulting API specifications will be described in the deliverable report D2.4 “Final API available for internal and external service providers”. One application of this semantic layer is the service discovery, which will be developed in parallel and can be queried to find out about data and tools available for a specific task, how to combine these into workflows and which services are running in an OpenRiskNet virtual research environment at any given time.

The applicability of the chosen concept and approaches, their implementation and issues which might occur are constantly tested and evaluated using a set of use cases (existing or under development), which will be adapted to the development stage of the APIs to use more and more of the advanced semantic interoperability features.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation*	Description
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
API	Application Programming Interface
BFO	Basic Formal Ontology
CDK	Chemistry Development Kit
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
JQ	Jaqpot Quatro
KE	Key Event
OWL	Web Ontology Language
QSAR	Quantitative structure–activity relationship
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSO	Single-sign-on
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

*OpenRiskNet Glossary is available at: <https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/home/wiki/Glossary>

REFERENCES

1. Hardy B, Douglas N, Helma C, Rautenberg M, Jeliaskova N, Jeliaskov V, et al. Collaborative development of predictive toxicology applications. *J Cheminform.* 2010;2: 7.
2. REST - Semantic Web Standards [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/wiki/REST>
3. Status codes in HTTP [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/Protocols/HTTP/HTRESP.html>
4. OpenTox API | OpenTox [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <http://opentox.net/opentox-api>
5. OpenTox API 1.2 resource ontology [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <http://opentox.org/api/1.2/opentox.owl>
6. Kohonen P, Benfenati E, Bower D, Ceder R, Crump M, Cross K, et al. The ToxBank Data Warehouse: Supporting the Replacement of In Vivo Repeated Dose Systemic Toxicity Testing. *Mol Inform.* 2013;32: 47–63.
7. ToxBank API Wiki [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <http://api.toxbank.net>
8. eNanoMapper | Computational infrastructure for toxicological data management of engineered nanomaterials [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: www.enanomapper.net
9. Jeliaskova N, Chomenidis C, Doganis P, Fadeel B, Grafström R, Hardy B, et al. The eNanoMapper database for nanomaterial safety information. *Beilstein J Nanotechnol.* Beilstein-Institut; 2015;6: 1609–1634.
10. Jaqpot Quattro Documentation [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <http://www.jaqpot.org:8080/jaqpot/swagger/>
11. Spjuth O, Rydberg P, Willighagen EL, Evelo CT, Jeliaskova N. XMetDB: an open access database for xenobiotic metabolism. *J Cheminform.* 2016;8: 47.
12. eNanoMapper API documentation [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <http://enanomapper.github.io/API/>
13. Helma C, Rautenberg M, Gebele D. nano-lazar: Read across predictions for nanoparticle toxicities with calculated and measured properties address. Submitted to *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2017; Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/250818>
14. Open PHACTS: semantic interoperability for drug discovery [Internet]. [cited 18 May 2017]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2012.05.016>
15. Azzaoui K, Jacoby E, Senger S, Rodríguez EC, Loza M, Zdrzil B, et al. Scientific competency questions as the basis for semantically enriched open pharmacological space development. *Drug Discov Today.* 2013;18: 843–852.
16. Willighagen EL, Waagmeester A, Spjuth O, Ansell P, Williams AJ, Tkachenko V, et al. The ChEMBL database as linked open data. *J Cheminform.* Springer International Publishing; 2013;5: 23.
17. Gaulton A, Hersey A, Nowotka M, Bento AP, Chambers J, Mendez D, et al. The ChEMBL database in 2017. *Nucleic Acids Res.* Oxford University Press; 2017;45: D945–D954.
18. Kutmon M, Riutta A, Nunes N, Hanspers K, Willighagen EL, Bohler A, et al. WikiPathways: capturing the full diversity of pathway knowledge. *Nucleic Acids Res.* Oxford University Press; 2016;44: D488–D494.
19. Waagmeester A, Kutmon M, Riutta A, Miller R, Willighagen EL, Evelo CT, et al. Using the Semantic Web for Rapid Integration of WikiPathways with Other Biological Online Data Resources. *PLoS Comput Biol.* Public Library of Science; 2016;12: e1004989.
20. UniProt: the universal protein knowledgebase. *Nucleic Acids Res.* Oxford University Press; 2017;45: D158–D169.
21. Batchelor C, Brenninkmeijer CYA, Chichester C, Davies M, Digles D, Dunlop I, et al. Scientific Lenses to Support Multiple Views over Linked Chemistry Data. *The Semantic Web – ISWC 2014.* Springer, Cham; 2014. pp. 98–113.
22. van Iersel MP, Pico AR, Kelder T, Gao J, Ho I, Hanspers K, et al. The BridgeDb framework: standardized access to gene, protein and metabolite identifier mapping services. *BMC Bioinformatics.* BioMed Central; 2010;11: 5.
23. Hastings J, Jeliaskova N, Owen G, Tsiliki G, Munteanu CR, Steinbeck C, et al. eNanoMapper: harnessing ontologies to enable data integration for nanomaterial risk

- assessment. *J Biomed Semantics*. BioMed Central; 2015;6: 10.
24. Gkoutos GV, Schofield PN, Hoehndorf R. The anatomy of phenotype ontologies: principles, properties and applications. *Brief Bioinform*. 2017; doi:10.1093/bib/bbx035
 25. Noy NF, Shah NH, Whetzel PL, Dai B, Dorf M, Griffith N, et al. BioPortal: ontologies and integrated data resources at the click of a mouse. *Nucleic Acids Res*. Oxford University Press; 2009;37: W170–W173.
 26. Cote R, Reisinger F, Martens L, Barsnes H, Vizcaino JA, Hermjakob H. The Ontology Lookup Service: bigger and better. *Nucleic Acids Res*. Oxford University Press; 2010;38: W155–W160.
 27. Slater L, Gkoutos GV, Schofield PN, Hoehndorf R. Using AberOWL for fast and scalable reasoning over BioPortal ontologies. *J Biomed Semantics*. BioMed Central; 2016;7: 49.
 28. Gkoutos GV, Green ECJ, Mallon A-M, Hancock JM, Davidson D. 10.1186/gb-2004-6-1-r8 [Internet]. *Genome Biol*. 2004. p. R8. doi:10.1186/gb-2004-6-1-r8
 29. Abeyruwan S, Vempati UD, Küçük-McGinty H, Visser U, Koleti A, Mir A, et al. Evolving BioAssay Ontology (BAO): modularization, integration and applications. *J Biomed Semantics*. BioMed Central; 2014;5: S5.
 30. Visser U, Abeyruwan S, Vempati U, Smith RP, Lemmon V, Schürer SC. BioAssay Ontology (BAO): a semantic description of bioassays and high-throughput screening results. *BMC Bioinformatics*. BioMed Central; 2011;12: 257.
 31. Hastings J, Chepelev L, Willighagen E, Adams N, Steinbeck C, Dumontier M. The Chemical Information Ontology: Provenance and Disambiguation for Chemical Data on the Biological Semantic Web. *PLoS One*. Public Library of Science; 2011;6: e25513.
 32. Buttigieg PL, Morrison N, Smith B, Mungall CJ, Lewis SE. The environment ontology: contextualising biological and biomedical entities. *J Biomed Semantics*. BioMed Central; 2013;4: 43.
 33. Ison J, Kalaš M, Jonassen I, Bolser D, Uludag M, McWilliam H, et al. EDAM: an ontology of bioinformatics operations, types of data and identifiers, topics and formats. *Bioinformatics*. Oxford University Press; 2013;29: 1325–1332.
 34. Ison J, Rapacki K, Ménager H, Kalaš M, Rydza E, Chmura P, et al. Tools and data services registry: a community effort to document bioinformatics resources. *Nucleic Acids Res*. Oxford University Press; 2016;44: D38–D47.
 35. Smith B. The basic tools of formal ontology. In: Guarino N, editor. *Formal Ontology in Information Systems*. IOS Press; 1998.
 36. Basic Formal Ontology - NCBO BioPortal [Internet]. [cited 24 May 2017]. Available: http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/BFO/?p=classes&conceptid=http%3A%2F%2Fpurl.obolibrary.org%2Fobo%2FBFO_0000001
 37. Malone J, Holloway E, Adamusiak T, Kapushesky M, Zheng J, Kolesnikov N, et al. Modeling sample variables with an Experimental Factor Ontology. *Bioinformatics*. Oxford University Press; 2010;26: 1112–1118.
 38. Mungall CJ, Torniai C, Gkoutos GV, Lewis SE, Haendel MA. Uberon, an integrative multi-species anatomy ontology. *Genome Biol*. BioMed Central; 2012;13: R5.
 39. Degtyarenko K, de Matos P, Ennis M, Hastings J, Zbinden M, McNaught A, et al. ChEBI: a database and ontology for chemical entities of biological interest. *Nucleic Acids Res*. Oxford University Press; 2008;36: D344–D350.
 40. Bizer C, Heath T, Berners-Lee T. Linked Data - The Story So Far. *Int J Semant Web Inf Syst*. 2009;5: 1–22.
 41. OAI. OAI/OpenAPI-Specification. In: GitHub [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <https://github.com/OAI/OpenAPI-Specification>
 42. Open API Initiative (OAI). In: Open API Initiative [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <https://www.Open Apis.org/>
 43. Hydra Core Vocabulary [Internet]. [cited 29 May 2017]. Available: <https://www.hydra-cg.com/spec/latest/core/>

ANNEXES

Use Cases Description

Here the current state of the three use cases will be outlined. Updated version can be obtained from the project website (<https://openrisknet.org>) and related pseudocode will be published at <https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/home/wiki/Use-Cases>.

Beside detailed descriptions, a use case template was developed to provide a uniform structure of the use case information. Sequence Diagrams were added to outline involved actors, services and processes.

Use Case Template

Diagram:

A sequence diagram that shows the interaction between objects (user, service and data) in operating order.

Name:

A clear verb/noun or actor/verb/noun descriptor that communicates the scope of the use case.

Brief Description:

A brief paragraph of text describing the scope of the use case.

Actors:

A list of the types of users who can engage in the activities described in the use case.

Preconditions:

Anything the solution can assume to be true when the use case begins.

Postconditions:

Anything that must be true when the use case is complete.

Success End Condition *(optional)*:

Failure End Condition *(optional)*:

Minimal Guarantee *(optional)*:

Basic Flow:

The set of steps the actors take to accomplish the goal of the use case. A clear description of what the system does in response to each user action.

Alternate Flows:

Capture the less common user/system interactions.

Exception Flows:

Things that can happen that prevent the user from achieving their goal.

Extensions *(optional)*:

Inputs *(optional)*:

Source *(optional)*:

Outputs *(optional)*:

Use Case 1: Merge existing data by a common structure identifier**Diagram:****Name:**

Merge existing data by a common structure identifier

Brief Description:

A user searches for existing assay information, selects the desired information, and merges the results based on a unique structure identifier.

Actors:

A researcher with background in toxicology.

Basic Flow:

The user supplies an identifier for a protein target, e.g. by name, UniProt ID, or ChEMBL ID, and searches ChEMBL for assays. The search result might be filtered with a number of simple constraints, e.g. words occurring in the description. The user selects the relevant assays. The assays are merged based on the common ChEMBL structure ID and the IC50 values. The results (structures and activity values) are stored as a new dataset and returned to the user.

Preconditions:

- Valid search criteria for the assay of interest
- A de-duplication strategy

Postconditions:

Success End Condition:

- At least one assay has been merged and the information has been returned

Failure End Condition:

- No assay has been found according to the supplied criteria
- No assay has been found according to the additional constraints

Minimal Guarantee:

- None

Relationship to other use cases:

The output of this use case could be an input to UC2.

Alternate Flows:

In case of duplicates, a strategy is required to resolve these multiple occurrences. To avoid to have to supply that strategy manually or during the search process, this strategy should be supplied in advance. The suggested merge strategy in case duplicates are encountered might be as follows:

- One assay has priority over another, ie. the order of the merge becomes important
- Merge using mean values only when values are consistent (e.g. within 2-SD range)
- Provide mechanism to interconvert data when specified as different data types (e.g. IC50 and Ki) or in different units (e.g. micromolar and nanomolar).
- Present all values and let user decide which to keep. Record user's choice.

Exception Flows:

Possible exceptions:

- No suitable assays are found: the system returns an error code
- The supplied parameters are out of scope: the system returns an error code
- Merging fails: the system returns an error code
- De-duplication fails: the system returns an error code
- Inconsistent de-duplication choices by the user: the system returns an error code

Extensions:

- Alternative assay providers such as PubChem can be used.
- Allow merging using canonical SMILES instead of ChEMBL structure identifier.
- The datasets retrieved contain different variants of the chemical structure (e.g. different salt forms). Before merging a standardized representation needs to be generated.
- Employ standardised units for merging using activity values
- Extend UC to be merged using categorical manner, i.e. active vs. inactive, mutagenic vs. non-mutagenic

Use Case 2: Building a (predictive) model**Diagram:****Name:**

Building and using a prediction model

Brief Description:

A user applies an algorithm to a dataset and uses the resulting model on a different dataset. The results are stored as novel dataset within the system.

Actors:

A researcher with background in model building.

Basic Flow:

The user selects an algorithm and a dataset within the system to induce a model. The selection of the algorithm is based on the intended uses, i.e. within a

supervised setting using a classification or regression algorithm. The algorithm possesses a number of default parameters, which can be adjusted to the users specifications. The user starts the induction process. Upon termination of the algorithm the user receives the result in form of a model. The user can supply an already existing second dataset and apply the model to it. The results are returned as novel dataset URI.

Preconditions:

- A dataset, identified by its URI, containing:
 - One or more substance (URIs) each with
 - a target feature (categorical/numerical)
 - optionally additional numerical features (URI)
- An existing algorithm with default parameters for:
 - Classification, requires
 - a categorical target feature
 - Regression, requires
 - a numerical target feature

Postconditions:**Success End Condition:**

- A model has been induced.
- If applicable, prediction on the second dataset have been produced and stored using this model.

Failure End Condition:

- No model has been induced.
- If applicable, no prediction on the second dataset could be produced and/or the results of applying the model to the second dataset could not be stored.

Minimal Guarantee:

- None

Relationship to other use cases:

When exchanging the actor *Researcher* to a validation algorithm, this use case could be part of a possible Validation use case.

Alternate Flows:

NA

Exception Flows:

Possible exceptions:

Alternative 1: Only applicable algorithms can be selected:

- The dataset is empty/not accessible: the system returns an error code
- The supplied parameters are out of scope: the system returns an error code

Alternative 2: User supplies dataset and algorithms without a selection process:

- *as above, but extra:*

- The supplied algorithm cannot be applied to the dataset: the system returns an error code

Extensions:

- Adopt model construction for Clustering
- Provide possibilities for feature construction
- Allow other types of features

Selecting a training data set:

- Include descriptor calculation services/APIs from SMILES (CDK), PDB files (crystallographic data, MOPAC), images (image analysis software).
- Preprocess (normalize or scale) of data.
- Include categorical features.
- Select subsets of the dataset (compounds and/or descriptors)
- Datasets are annotated with the the type of variables that they contain (numerical/categorical)

Use Case 3: Search and Retrieve Assay Data based on Ontological Terms

Diagram:

Name:

Search and Retrieve Molecular Data linked to Key Events in AOPs using assay ontology terms

Brief Description:

A user wants to look up omics data for a particular bioassay. The user supplies a particular assay type, fetches related ontological terms from an ontology service, and retrieves all available assay data associated with assay types and terms. The use case is aimed at nanomaterials, but can be extended to other chemical substances, including compounds.

Actors:

A researcher with background in toxicology and assay technologies.

Basic Flow:

The user starts with a type of assay, like a genotoxicity assay. This term is looked up in an ontology service (i.e. containing the eNanoMapper ontology or the BioAssay Ontology) and the results are used to retrieve matching assays using the assay service (i.e. containing the nanosafety data repository). Using these results, the assay service is employed to retrieve data annotated with the specific ontology terms. Furthermore, the call to the ontology service may return multiple term IRIs if a full ontological hierarchy is requested. This simplifies asking all genotoxicity assay data, even if data is annotated with more specific genotoxicity assay terms.

Preconditions:

- The supplied assay type is a valid ontological term

Postconditions:

Success End Condition:

- Assay data is found for (engineered) nanomaterials

Failure End Condition:

- No assay data for the ontological terms can be found within the system

Minimal Guarantee:

- None

Relationship to other use cases:

Search results will allow downloading of data that may be used (after further preprocessing) as input to QSAR studies.

Alternate Flows:

- Directly use an ontological term for searching
- Assay type might occur in multiple ontologies, a workflow for the selection of the intended ontology might be required

Exception Flows:

- Possible exceptions
 - No matching assays are found. An empty set of results

Extensions:

- Support for chemicals other than nanomaterials.
- Search for chemicals based on KE-related genes and/or protein targets.
- Search for chemicals based on Gene Ontology terms (instead of specific genes).
- An AOP is given and an additional Service is used to request the assays associated or genes/targets associated with the KEs in that AOP.